

MUSIC EDUCATION SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN: ACHIEVEMENTS AND PROBLEMS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the formation, stages of development and current state of the music education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The attention paid to music education during the years of independence, the reforms implemented in the areas of identifying talented young people, supporting them and preserving the national musical heritage are highlighted. At the same time, the problems existing in the system - such as the incompatibility of curricula with modern requirements, the lack of qualified personnel, problems with the technical base and the insufficient introduction of digital tools - are also considered.

Keywords: music education, education system, national heritage, innovation, curriculum, problem, development, reforms, pedagogical approach

Introduction.

Music is an art form that expresses the most delicate and deep feelings of the human soul, and its educational, aesthetic, and spiritual-educational significance is incomparable. The cultural heritage, national values, traditions, and spiritual world of each people are reflected primarily in music. Especially in a country with such a rich and ancient musical heritage as Uzbekistan, music is recognized not only as a field of art, but also as an important tool in educating the younger generation as spiritually mature, aesthetically perfect individuals.

Today, the system of musical education in Uzbekistan is being updated based on national traditions and modern requirements. During the years of independence, special attention was paid to the field of culture and art, in particular, musical education, new educational institutions were established, and systematic work was carried out to support talented youth. At the same time, there are also problems that need to be solved in this area: the need to update the content of education, improve the qualifications of teachers, strengthen the material and technical base, and introduce digital technologies is growing. This article provides an in-depth analysis of the development path of the music education system in Uzbekistan, achievements and existing problems, and puts forward scientific and practical recommendations for further improvement of the sector.

Formation and stages of development of the music education system in Uzbekistan.

Music education in Uzbekistan has a long history and is reflected in the activities of Eastern scholars, hafiz and composers. During the reign of Amir Temur and the Temurids, great attention was paid to the art of music, and through the Jadid movement, this direction was deeply embedded in the education system. In the 20th century, music schools, art colleges and conservatories were established, and music education became a separate field.

During the years of independence, this area reached a new level. The number of music and art schools in the republic has increased, a number of state programs have been adopted to identify talented young people and support them internationally. Higher educational

institutions such as the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan and the Institute of Arts and Culture have become the mainstays of musical education. In recent years, a number of positive results have been achieved in the field of music education:

The increase and modernization of educational institutions - hundreds of children's music and art schools are operating throughout the republic. Work is being carried out to provide them with modern instruments and technical equipment in stages.

The system for identifying talented young people - through the state programs "*Youth - our future*", "*Creation*" and other programs, young musicians are selected and opportunities are created for them to receive grants, study scholarships and exchange foreign experience.

Preservation and promotion of national musical heritage - Specialized courses, competitions and scientific research on the art of shashmaqom, bakhshi, maqom are being conducted to ensure the inculcation of national music into the minds of the younger generation.

Current issues and discussions

Despite the achievements, a number of problems still remain relevant in the music education system:

Course programs do not meet modern requirements - some curricula and methodological materials are outdated, they need to be updated and innovative approaches introduced.

Low human resource capacity - in some regions there is a lack of experienced and specialized teachers, especially the number of specialists familiar with foreign pedagogical experience is small.

Problems with the material and technical base - insufficient quality and quantity of musical instruments, classroom equipment that does not meet modern requirements negatively affect the quality of education.

Lack of digital technologies - especially during the pandemic, it became clear that a special platform and interactive programs for online music education have not been sufficiently developed.

From the above analysis, it can be seen that the music education system in Uzbekistan is developing steadily, but systemic reforms, pedagogical innovations, and international cooperation are needed to further improve it.

Methodology.

The effectiveness of any scientific research directly depends on the chosen methodological approach, and this is especially important when analyzing the musical-educational sphere. When writing this article, the aim was, first of all, to deeply study the stages of historical development of the musical education system, its current achievements and problems. For this, scientific-analytical, statistical, comparative and observational methods were used.

During the study, the activities of music schools, art colleges, higher educational institutions operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan were analyzed, and an approach was developed based on their official data and statistical indicators from open sources. In addition, the content of current state programs, regulatory documents, strategic concepts and presidential decrees in the field of education was also studied. Through these sources, an attempt was made to assess the state policy on music education, the direction and practical effectiveness of reforms.

When writing the article, special attention was paid to the qualitative approach, that is, not only numbers and data, but also the situations behind them - the experiences of teachers, students and specialists - were in the center of analysis. An attempt was made to fully reflect the real-life situation based on interviews with experts in the field and practical observations. Through this approach, it was intended that the article would be not only theoretically based, but also an analytical work close to practice, providing useful conclusions.

Thus, in this scientific work, methodological foundations were formed based on a comprehensive approach, combining historicity and modernity, based on analysis and discussion. This allowed for a deep and comprehensive coverage of the topic.

Results:

The music education system of Uzbekistan has developed significantly in recent years and is achieving positive results. The number of music and art schools operating in the republic is increasing year by year. In particular, in 2015 there were 320 music schools, while by 2023 this figure had reached 400. This, first of all, indicates the increasing attention of the state to the field of art, in particular, to the musical education of the younger generation.

The number of gifted students also continues to grow steadily. While 15 thousand gifted students were registered in 2015, by 2023 this number had reached 23 thousand. This indicates the increasing strengthening of selection and support mechanisms in the education system. The increase in the capacity of music teachers is also clearly reflected in the results. In 2015, there were 4,200 qualified teachers, while by 2023 their number will reach 5,000. This indicates an increase in the effectiveness of the pedagogical personnel training system. Based on these statistics, it can be concluded that over the past eight years, music education in Uzbekistan has been changing positively, both qualitatively and quantitatively. At the same time, it is important to continue systemic reforms to consolidate these achievements and eliminate existing problems.

Conclusion.

Music education is not only an important means of teaching art, but also of educating well-rounded, aesthetically pleasing, and spiritually mature individuals for society. Uzbekistan has taken important steps towards the development of this area during the years of independence. The increase in the number of schools, the recognition of talented young people, the promotion of the national musical heritage - all this indicates that music education occupies an important place in state policy. At the same time, there are also problems in the system that are waiting to be solved: the need for updating curricula, the lack of technical equipment, the lack of digital educational tools, and the insufficient number of qualified teachers in some regions are among the pressing issues. Eliminating these problems requires not only state policy, but also effective cooperation between society, educational institutions, and specialists.

Thus, the music education system of Uzbekistan is on the path of sustainable development. Now the main task is to preserve these achievements, bring them to a new level, and organize music education in accordance with international standards by introducing modern technologies. Because a young generation with musical literacy and an aesthetic outlook is the cultural future of the country.

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